

Synthesis of New Benzothiazole and Condensed Benzothiazole Derivatives

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In conjunction to a project directed toward the synthesis of heterocyclic systems with expected biological activity¹, the present work reports on the annelation and functionalisation of 2-aminobenzothiazole. It has been reported that thiazole derivatives form 1 : 1 Michael adduct with π -acceptor^{2,3} and the effect of both amino group and thiazole

ring nitrogen on the basicity of the donors explained. Thus, cycloaddition of the benzothiazole (1) and benzyldenemalononitrile afforded the thiazolopyrimidine³ (2).

The formation of 2 presumably takes place as illustrated in Scheme 1. This involves the presumably of Michael acyclic adduct which undergoes intramolecular cycloaddition

Scheme 1

to afford **2**. Refluxing of thiazole **1** and ethyl cyanoacetate in presence of sodium ethoxide furnished thiazolopyrimidine⁴. Cycloaddition of **3** and benzylidenmalononitrile in presence of base provided pyridopyrimidine **4**.

Pyrimidopyrimidine **5** was obtained by reacting the thiazolopyrimidine (**3**) and benzoyl isothiocyanate in refluxing dioxane. This transformation involves the addition of activated enaminone **3** to electrophilic carbon of benzoyl isothiocyanate to afford the non-isolable thioamide (A) that undergoes intramolecular cycloaddition to give pyrimidopyrimidine⁵. Compound **1** cyclised to give thiazolopyrimidine **6** by refluxing with acetylenedicarboxylic acid. Thiourea derivatives (**7a-c**) were obtained by addition of aminobenzothiazole (**1**) to aroyl isothiocyanates. Compounds **7a, b** were cyclised to thiazotriazines (**8a, b**) by refluxing in butanol. Depending on the reaction condition, **7c** cyclised to give either pyrimidine or thiazine moiety. Thus, refluxing of **7c** and sodium ethoxide produced pyrimidine derivative **9**. While keeping of **7c** in ethanolic sodium ethoxide solution afforded thiazine **10**.

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Pyc-Unicam spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian HA100 spectrometer (200 MHz). Microanalysis was carried out at Microanalytical Unit, Faculty of Science, Cairo University. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

Thiazolopyrimidine (2): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml), triethylamine (0.5 ml) and benzylidenmalononitrile (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 4 h. The solid product obtained after cooling was crystallised from acetic acid, (55%), m.p. 105°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 560 (C=N), 2 240 (C≡N), 3 000 (CH), 3 200–3 400 cm⁻¹ (NH₂); δ 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.2 (1H, s, CH-pyrimidine), 6.3 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.4–7.9 (8H, m, ArH).

Thiazolopyrimidine (3): To a solution of sodium (0.01 mol) in dry methanol (30 ml), compound **1** (0.01 mol) and ethyl cyanoacetate (0.01 mol) were added and the resulting solution was refluxed for 5 h. After cooling, it was diluted with water (100 ml), filtered and acidified with acetic acid. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, (60%), m.p. 224°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 560 (C=N), 1 690 (C=O), 3 200–3 400 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.46 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.2–7.9 (3H, m, ArH), 9.25 (1H, br s, NH).

Pyridopyrimidine (4): A mixture of **3** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml), triethylamine (0.5 ml) and benzylidenmalononitrile (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 4 h. The solid obtained after cooling was crystallised from acetic acid, (50%), m.p. >300°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 560 (C=N), 1 690 (C=O), 2 240 (C≡N), 3 200–3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH₂); δ 2.59 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.2–8.0 (8H, m, ArH), 9.6 (2H, br s, NH₂).

Pyrimidopyrimidine (5): A mixture of **3** (0.01 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) in dioxane (30 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The mixture was then poured in water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 142°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 550 (C=N), 1 680 (C=O), 1 910 (C=S), 2 235 (C≡N); δ 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.2–8.0 (8H, m, ArH).

Thiazolopyrimidine (6): A solution of **1** (0.01 mol) and acetylenedicarboxylic acid (0.012 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. After cooling, the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 252°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 630 (C=C), 1 665, 1 680 (C=O), 3 200–3 300 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.2 (1H, s, CH-pyrimidine), 7.2–7.5 (3H, m, ArH), 11.3 (1H, s, COOH).

Thiourea derivatives (7a-c): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and aroyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) in dioxane (30 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in water and the solid so formed was crystallised from appropriate solvents to yield the products (50–60%): **7a**, m.p. 158–60°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 560 (C=N), 1 680 (C=O), 1 910 (C=S), 3 200–3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.3–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 9.2–9.6 (1H, br s, NH); **b**, 180°; **c**, >300°.

Thiazotriazine (8a, b): A solution of **7a/b** (0.01 mol) in n-butanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. After cooling, the precipitate formed was crystallised from n-butanol: **8a** (60%), m.p. 190°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 560 (C=N), 1 910 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ 2.8 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.5–7.8 (8H, m, ArH); **b**, (60%), 210°.

Pyrimidine (9): A mixture of **7c** (0.01 mol) and sodium ethoxide (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 5 h. It was then poured in ice-cold HCl (10 ml; 20%) and the resulting solid product was crystallised from ethanol, (50%), m.p. >300°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 560 (C=N), 1 680 (C=O), 1 910 (C=S), 2 940 (CH₂), 3 200–3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.1 (1H, m, pyrimidine 5-H), 4.6 (1H, m, CH), 7.1–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 10.0 (1H, br s, cyclic NH).

Thiazine (10): A mixture of **7c** (0.01 mol) and sodium ethoxide (0.01 mol) was left at room temperature overnight. It was then acidified by ice-cold HCl (10 ml; 20%) and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (50%). m.p. >300°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 550 (C=N), 1 690 (C=O), 3 200–3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.12 (2H, m, CH₂), 4.6 (1H, m, CH), 7.1–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 9.2 (1H, br s, NH).

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